

Postharvest Biology and Technology

POSTHARVEST UV-B AND UV-C RADIATION ENHANCED THE BIOSYNTHESIS OF GLUCOSINOLATES AND ISOTHIOCYANATES IN BRASSICACEAE SPROUTS

--Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>The objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of UV lighting (UV-B, UV-C and UV-C + UV-B) as a postharvest abiotic stress in the quality changes of minimally processed Brassicaceae sprouts (broccoli and radish) during a shelf-life period of 10 d at 4 °C. No UV illumination was used as control (CTRL). The total UV-C doses received were 9 kJ m⁻² (UVC) and 15 kJ m⁻² UV-B (UVB) by applying the 50% of such doses after harvest and on the first day of the shelf-life. Results showed that when UVC was applied, the epiphytic microbial load was reduced up to 1 log CFU g⁻¹ fw. The UVB treatment reported the highest total phenolic content (TPC) and total antioxidant capacity (TAC) after 10 d at 4 °C. In general, both species showed an amelioration effect in the TPC and TAC after UV treatments, which also enhanced the glucosinolate (GL) and the main isothiocyanates (ITC) content. In fact, UVB increased by ~30 % the GL content compared to CTRL samples, which were mostly aliphatic GLs in radish and indolyl GLs in broccoli. As main ITC, sulforaphane content was enhanced by 37.5 % in UVB-treated broccoli sprouts while the sulforaphane content was highly increased by 72 % in radish sprouts. In conclusion, UVB radish sprouts reported 5-fold higher GL content and 60-fold higher biologically ITC content than broccoli sprouts. Therefore, its inclusion in the daily intake is recommended to increase the prevention of chronic inflammatory diseases.</p>
Suggested Reviewers:	<p>Luis Cisneros, Dr. Texas A&M University College Station lcisnero@tamu.edu</p> <p>Daniel Jacobo-Velázquez, Dr. Instituto Tecnológico y de Estudios Superiores de Monterrey: Instituto Tecnológico y de Estudios Superiores de Monterrey djacobov@itesm.mx</p> <p>Arturo Duarte-Sierra, Dr. Université Laval: Université Laval arturo.duarte-sierra@fsaa.ulaval.ca</p>
Opposed Reviewers:	
Response to Reviewers:	<p>Dear Editor and Reviewers:</p> <p>We are pleased to submit the answers to the issues raised in the comments of our manuscript 'POSTHARVEST UV-B AND UV-C RADIATION ENHANCED THE BIOSYNTHESIS OF GLUCOSINOLATES AND ISOTHIOCYANATES IN BRASSICACEAE SPROUTS'.</p> <p>We really appreciate your comments that have improved the manuscript. We have considered all the suggestions to clarify our data. We are including a revised manuscript with the amendments in the text concerning the proposed changes. Find attached the manuscript with our responses to editor' and reviewers' comments.</p>

Sincerely yours,

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February 22nd, 2021

Dear Editor:

I am pleased to submit our article '**POSTHARVEST UV-B AND UV-C RADIATION ENHANCED THE BIOSYNTHESIS OF GLUCOSINOLATES AND ISOTHIOCYANATES IN BRASSICACEAE SPROUTS**'. The authors Lorena Martínez-Zamora, Noelia Castillejo, and myself agree to its submission to the highly appreciated **Postharvest Biology and Technology** Journal. This work is an original research carried out by the authors. All authors agree with the contents of the manuscript and its submission to this Journal. All listed Authors have significantly contributed to the work and agree to be in the author list. No part of the research has been published in any form elsewhere.

The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of UV lighting (UV-B, UV-C and UV-C + UV-B) as a postharvest abiotic stress in the quality changes of minimally processed *Brassicaceae* sprouts (broccoli and radish) during a shelf-life period of 10 days at 4 °C. The novelty of this work lies on UV-C and UV-B radiation hormesis in the biosynthesis of nutraceutical compounds while maintaining the optimum quality of broccoli and radish sprouts.

As main results, both species showed an amelioration effect in the TPC and TAC after UV treatments, which also enhanced the glucosinolate and the main isothiocyanates content. In fact, as main ITC, sulforaphane content was enhanced by 37.5 % in UVB-treated broccoli sprouts while the sulforaphane content was highly increased by 72 % in radish sprouts under the same treatment.

In conclusion, UVB radish sprouts reported 5-fold higher GL content and 60-fold higher biologically ITC content than broccoli sprouts. Therefore, its inclusion in the daily intake is recommended to increase the prevention of chronic inflammatory diseases.

Furthermore, the industrial relevance of the present study lies on the improvement of the nutritional quality of *Brassicaceae* sprouts under low doses of postharvest UV-C and UV-B lighting. Since the consumers demand for functional foods able to improve their health, especially during the pandemic caused by SARS-COV 2, food industry has focused on looking for new techniques to improve the biosynthesis of phytochemicals, such as glucosinolates and isothiocyanates.

We hope that you agree on the merits and appropriateness of this study for publication in this journal.

Looking forward to your comments, sincerely yours

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July 8th, 2021

Dear Editor:

We are pleased to submit the answers to the issues raised in the comments of our manuscript '**POSTHARVEST UV-B AND UV-C RADIATION ENHANCED THE BIOSYNTHESIS OF GLUCOSINOLATES AND ISOTHIOCYANATES IN BRASSICACEAE SPROUTS**'.

We really appreciate your comments that will surely improve the manuscript. We have considered all the suggestions to clarify our data. We are including a revised manuscript with the amendments in the text concerning the proposed changes. Find below a list of our responses to reviewers' comments.

Sincerely yours,

Prof. Dr. Francisco Artés-Hernández
Universidad Politécnica de Cartagena. Spain.

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Reviewer #1: The manuscript reports that postharvest UVB and UVC treatment of broccoli and radish sprouts enhance glucosinolate content and reduce microbial load. This research confirms previous studies of UVB and UVC effects on glucosinolate accumulation, and antimicrobial load. However, current version of this paper somehow lacks novelty.

Firstly, we would like to point out that a novelty of our study according to previous manuscripts of the bibliography is the simultaneous postharvest application of UV-C + UV-B lighting to increase the glucosinolate accumulation in crucifer sprouts, which has never been reported before.

Some mechanistic studies are needed.

Thank you very much for your comments; we will consider your appreciation to study the mechanistic processes of the biosynthesis of these compounds in future studies. However, we initially wanted to focus this work to study the 'effects induced by the treatments' by determining postharvest quality and the accumulation of such bioactive compounds. We performed many analyses, and the goal of our research was different from the mechanistic.

The specific comments are as follows.

1. Fig 4 (now Fig. 3), why more antioxidants were observed after day 4 storage?

UV light acts as an abiotic stressor. Under UV effect, plants biosynthesise antioxidant compounds as endogenous defence mechanisms. Such mechanisms produce reactive oxygen species (ROS), which continue acting during the storage (from 0 to 10 d) and

higher levels of phenolic compounds are accumulated during this time to protect the plant to the end of the shelf life (Moreira-Rodríguez et al., 2017a).

According to your suggestion, we have clarified this issue in L 444-447.

Moreira-Rodríguez, M., Nair, V., Benavides, J., Cisneros-Zevallos, L., Jacobo-Velázquez, D.A., 2017a. UVA, UVB light, and methyl jasmonate, alone or combined, redirect the biosynthesis of glucosinolates, phenolics, carotenoids, and chlorophylls in broccoli sprouts. Int. J. Mol. Sci. 18, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms18112330>

2. Microbial load and shelf-life results should be presented in Results section, not in discussion. Need a table or figure to show the results.

According to your suggestion, we have included a table to show the microbial load of the studied sprouts in Supplementary Material (Table S1 for broccoli sprouts and Table S2 radish sprouts).

3. Day 0 data: On day 0, all the parameters showed big variation for control and treatments. So, when did authors got the samples after UV treatment on day 0? It should not have some much changes on day 0 for all the samples.

We applied the UV treatment on day 0 and after 1 hour of acclimation, the sprouts were frozen (L147-150 of the 2.2. section). This period could be enough to the plant to produce the bioactive compounds necessities to counteract the stress caused by UV on day 0.

4. Other minor issues:

a. too many "in fact" in the paper. We have revised all "in fact" and we have eliminated or changed those that were not necessary.

b. Line 62, delete "to". Done

c. Line 65, delete "in this way". Done

d. Line, delete "for that". Done in L 71

e. Line 250-262, rewrite the sentence. Done

f. Table 1 and Figure 2 should be put in Results section. Table 1 and Figure 2 have been moved to Results section. Now, Figure 2 has been changed as Figure 4.

Reviewer #2: General opinion

The authors present convincing results regarding the effect of UV-C light on microorganisms and regarding the effect of UV B light on glucosinolates. The authors present a lot of experimental data and the goal of their research has been achieved.

Thank you very much for your comments.

I suggest a number of improvements to the discussion of the results. Currently we have reliable information about the effect of UV B light on the physiology of plants in pre and post-harvest that have not been taken into account. I suggest substantially enriching the discussion of the results presented here regarding the metabolism of phenolic compounds. The effect of UVB light on the metabolism of phenolic compounds is a well-known event. Some of the many published works on this topic are (and many more...):

"Changing scenario in plant UV-B research: UV-B from a generic stressor to a specific regulator" Parihar et al. Elsevier Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology B: Biology. Volume 153, December 2015, Pages 334-343 "Post-

harvest UV-B irradiation induces changes of phenol contents and corresponding biosynthetic gene expression in peaches and nectarines". Scattino et al., Food Chemistry, Volume 163, 15 November 2014, Pages 51-60.

"UVR8 mediated plant protective responses under low UV-B radiation leading to photosynthetic acclimation" Singh et al., Elsevier Journal of Photochemistry and Photobiology B: Biology. Volume 137, August 2014, Pages 67-76

"The UV-B Photoreceptor UVR8: From Structure to Physiology" Gareth I. Jenkins. The Plant Cell, Volume 26, Issue 1, January 2014, Pages 21-37, <https://doi.org/10.1105/tpc.113.119446>

"Photomorphogenic responses to ultraviolet-B light" Jenkins, G. I. (2017). Plant, Cell and Environment, 40(11), pp. 2544-2557.

"UV-B Irradiation Changes Specifically the Secondary Metabolite Profile in Broccoli Sprouts: Induced Signaling Overlaps with Defense Response to Biotic Stressors" Mewis et al., Plant Cell Physiol. 2012 Sep; 53(9): 1546-1560.

We really thank your comments. We have improved the discussion section about the effect of UVB light on the metabolism of phenolic compounds by adding all the works that you have recommend us.

Another point to consider is the comparison between both species. I would not emphasize whether the results were better for radish than for broccoli and vice versa, since the treatment is actually good for both cases.

We have explained the UV effects on the two studied models. However, we have emphasized that the UV treatment is good for both cases as you point out. L 271, 360-361, 368, 396-397.

Some specific details:

Introduction

1) 42-43 This sentence needs a reference. **Added.**

2) 64-65 This sentence It is not related to the proposal of the work where the use of UV and not photosynthetically active light is pointed out. I would take it out. o tiene relación con el planteo del trabajo donde se apunta al uso de UV y no de luz fotosintéticamente activa.

We have removed this sentence.

Materials and methods

3) How the total effective dose of 9 kJ m⁻² 137 UV-C was measured? I suppose that the material of the basket must absorb UV light maybe the doses have to be corrected since I understand that the two applications were made with the baskets closed. Clarify it.

You are right, both applications were made with the sprouts sited into the closed trays and the total effective dose of 9 kJ m⁻² was measured inside the trays. We have clarified it in the manuscript (L 123-126 and 131, 134, and 138).

Results

4) There is an error in the legend of figure 2.

We have corrected the error in Figure 2, which is now Figure 4.

5) 285-287 " From a general point of view, the TAC of the studied sprouts increased during the germination, but when they reach the optimal vegetative growth as a ready to eat sprout, their TAC was maintained during the postharvest storage at 4 °C". This statement is correct for broccoli but not for radish... .It needs to be clarified.

We have clarified this sentence in L 284-288

Discusión

6) The first two sentences do not keep connection with the rest. Are they necessary at the beginning of the discussion? I'd take them out.

We have moved this sentence at a better part of the discussion section. Now, it is placed in L 410-412.

7) 413 416 "From a general point of view, the TPC increased after UVC and UVC+B treatments on minimally processed broccoli and radish sprouts, respectively, which can be due to the better extraction of phenolic compounds after plant cells disruption provoked by UV". I do not agree with this explanation... ..The same authors give another explanation below.

We have removed this sentence and we have focused our explanation on the second sentences which, as you say, fits better with the explanation of the effect of UV on plants. L 413 - 421.

8) In general, the discussion still needs to relate the results to what is known about the effect of UV light on secondary metabolism.

According to your suggestions, we have improved the discussion section about the effect of UV light on secondary metabolism. We have included, among other articles, those that you recommended above.

Reviewer #3: The manuscript "POSTHARVEST UV-B AND UV-C RADIATION ENHANCED THE BIOSYNTHESIS OF GLUCOSINOLATES AND ISOTHIOCYANATES IN BRASSICACEAE SPROUTS" aimed at determining if exposure of broccoli and radish sprouts to UVB, UVC or their combination before storage can increase their contents of nutraceutical compounds, e.g., glucosinolates and isothiocyanates. The results of this work show that exposure to UVB, UVC or both in combination do increase the contents of these compounds in sprouts stored for 10 days at 4°C. These results have important potential applications and may warrant publication in PBT, however, there are a number of points that need to be revised before the manuscript can be accepted.

Thank you for your comments. According to your suggestions, we have improved our manuscript as follows:

-1 In general, it would be advisable to have the language style checked by a native speaker, there are a number of awkward sentences and grammar mistakes.

We have revised all manuscript.

-2 Lines 66-69, this sentence implies that antioxidant enzymes are responsible for the accumulation of phenolic acids, GLs, etc, is this correct? Is there a causal effect of antioxidant enzymes (e.g., SOD) increasing the accumulation of the compounds mentioned in this sentence?

We have rewritten the sentence to clarify it (L65-67).

-3 starting on line 124, does this mean that UVC and UVB reached the sprouts from above and from below? Or one type of UV was placed below the sprouts, the other one above? Next there is a reference to a net, does this mean that sprouts were placed on a transparent net? This is crucial for any reader trying to repeat this experiment and should be more clearly explained.

This information has been clarified in L115-121

The detailed description of the radiation chamber is in:

Formica-Oliveira, A.C., Martínez-Hernández, G.B., Díaz-López, V., Artés, F., Artés-Hernández, F., 2017b. Use of postharvest UV-B and UV-C radiation treatments to revalorize broccoli byproducts and edible florets. Innov. Food Sci. Emerg. Technol. 43, 77–83. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifset.2017.07.036>

The schematic representation of the UV radiation chamber is:

Also, this scheme is reported in our previous publications (Martínez-Hernández et al., 2020) which can help you to understand our self-made UV radiation chamber. However, in this case, the radiation chamber was equipped with UV-C lamps since we have the possibility to change the UV light in our prototype.

Fig. 1. Prototype of UV-C chamber with two banks of UV-C lamps.

Martínez-Hernández, G.B., Blanco, V., Blaya-Ros, P.J., Torres-Sánchez, R., Domingo, R., Artés-Hernández, F., 2020. Effects of Uv-C on Bioactive Compounds and Quality Changes During Shelf Life of Sweet Cherry Grown Under Conventional or Regulated Deficit Irrigation. Sci. Hort. (Amsterdam). 269, 109398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2020.109398>

In our case, the radiation chamber was equipped with 12 UV-B unfiltered emitting lamps (TL 40W/01 RS; Philips, Eindhoven, The Netherlands) and 18 UV-C unfiltered emitting lamps (TUV 36W/G36 T8; Philips, Eindhoven, The Netherlands) intercalated above and below the radiation chamber. According to your suggestion, this description has been clarified in Section 2.2. by citing previous authors to avoid plagiarism.

-4 line 332, "... The initial total GL content was 291 g kg⁻¹ dw in the radish seed ..." is this so? 29% of dry matter was accounted for by GL ?

It is correct. The radish seed reported a higher GL content than 10-day sprouts and 29% of seed dry matter was accounted for by GL content. In the case of broccoli seed, there is no significant increase between seed and 10-day sprouts. Although the results obtained for radish are slightly higher than those of other authors are, the same method, curve standard, and HPLC protocol were used for the extraction and quantification of GL content from both species. The GL content accounted a 16.7 and 4 % of dry matter of 10-day radish and broccoli sprouts, respectively. UV treatments increased the GL content of radish sprouts, obtaining similar values to those of seed.

We have clarified it in the manuscript in L 337-338.

-5 lines 365-366: I don't quite understand this sentence, if samples contain 0,05 g kg⁻¹ of sulforaphane, what does it mean "accounting the 8% of the total sulphoraphane content"??

The total sulforaphane content was calculated as the sum of sulforaphane and sulforaphane nitrile. Sulforaphane (broccoli) or sulforaphene (radish) is the biologically active compound. Therefore, we can highlight that only 8% of the total sulforaphane / sulforaphene content is represented by the biologically active compound, the 92 % has been identified as the nitrile form.

We have clarified in the manuscript in L 376.

-6 lines 390-391: this sentence implies that these are results from the authors of this paper, but Samec et al., is a paper from other authors....

We have checked this sentence and moved it to L 418-420

-7 line 412: the authors speculate that the increase of total phenolics content in sprouts irradiated with UV may be due to cell disruption, however, the authors claim there was no photodamage (line 397), these two arguments are contradictory at first sight.

We have clarified this explanation. We have removed the sentence mentioned above and focused our explanation on the relation between phenol biosynthesis and PAL activation after UV abiotic stress application. L421-436

-8 lines 464-465: who may share what? UVB and UVC share UVR8 as photoreceptor?? this should be streamlined....

We have clarified this. The action spectrum of UVR8 is ranged from 250 to 310 nm, where UV-C region is included (Jiang et al., 2012), which suggests that both radiations may share such receptor. L 483-485.

9- lines 468-470: I can't understand this reasoning, if UVC and UVB shared UVR8 as photoreceptor, this could explain similar effects of UVB and UVC. But this is contradicted by the idea that UVC might block UVR8, these ideas should be explained better.

We have explained it better L 489-493.

I also attach the original submission with comments and questions.

Thanks for your comments in the original submission. We have corrected all the appreciations marked in PDF.

Please, find below the responses and changes that we have performed according to your comments in the PDF:

1. Brassicaceae ?? L42: "in *Brassica* genus" has been modified
2. are abbreviations explained in the text? If so, GL should be explained.... L38: GL has been described as glucosinolate
3. because ITC are synthesized from GLs by myrosinases ?? L41 It has been properly modified
4. a high percentage of ??? L45: "of GLs" has been specified
5. of GL? Yes, it has been added in L45
6. something is missing in this sentence: L49-51 have been modified to: "In addition, ITC and indolyl compounds (hydrolytic products of GLs) act as anti-inflammatory compounds, and allow the apoptosis of cancer cells due to their positive role modulating cell cycles"
7. another? L55: "From a different point of view" have been modified
8. this sentence implies that antioxidant enzymes are responsible for the accumulation of phenolic acids, GLs, etc, is this correct?? We have rewritten the sentence to clarify that both substances (enzymes and bioactive compounds) are induced by UV.
9. root ??? changed in Table 1
10. does this mean that UVC and UVB reached the sprouts from above and from below?? Or one type of UV was placed below the sprouts, the other one above??

As also described in our previous comments:

The radiation chamber was equipped with 6 UV-B unfiltered emitting lamps (TL 40W/01 RS; Philips, Eindhoven, The Netherlands) and 9 UV-C unfiltered emitting lamps (TUV 36W/G36 T8; Philips, Eindhoven, The Netherlands) intercalated above and below of the radiation chamber, as the next Figure shown:

According to your suggestion, this description has been clarified in Section 2.2. by citing previous authors to avoid plagiarism.

11. which net???

As shown in the next Figure, a net was sited in the middle of the radiation chamber in order to accommodate the product during the UV treatment.

Fig. 1. Prototype of UV-C chamber with two banks of UV-C lamps.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scienta.2020.109398>

12. is the abbreviation "DPPH" already explained?? In a quick search, I couldn't find the explanation, if that's the case, please include this explanation before the first use of the abbreviation...**Included**

13. rephrase, e.g., UVB had higher TAC.... ??? **Done**

14. what are "the two UV applications"?? Does this refer to applications on day 0 and day 1?? **Exactly. It has been clarified in L299-300**

15. is this so???

29% of dry matter accounted for by GL???

It is correct. The radish seed reported a higher GL content than 10-day sprouts and 29% of seed dry matter was accounted for by GL content. Although the results obtained for radish are slightly higher than those of other authors, the same method, curve standard, and HPLC protocol were used for the extraction and quantification of GL content from both species. The GL content accounted a 16.7 and 4 % of dry matter of 10-day radish and broccoli sprouts, respectively. UV treatments increased the GL content of radish sprouts, obtaining similar values to those of seed. We have clarified it in the manuscript in L 337-338.

16. I don't quite understand this, if samples contain 0,05 g kg⁻¹ of sulforaphane, what does it mean "accounting the 8% of the total sulphoraphane content"

We have clarified that is sulforaphane, as biologically active compound, in L378

17. this sentence implies that these are results from the authors of this paper, but Samec et al., is a paper from other authors....

This sentence has been removed

18. differences through time or between different treatments??

It has been clarified in L407

19. increases of ???? It has been clarified in L439

20. this is speculative, isn't it ??Yes. It has been clarified in L443-445

21. who may share?? UVB and UVC share UVR8 as photoreceptor?? this should be streamlined....It has been clarified in L485-488

22. I can't quite understand this reasoning, if UVC and UVB shared UVR8 as photoreceptor, this could explain similar effects of UVB and UVC. But this is contradicted by the idea that UVC might block UVR8, these ideas should be explained much better... It has been clarified in L485-488

23. what is converting ratio???It has been clarified in L514

HIGHLIGHTS

- Postharvest UV-B and C increased the total phenolic content and antioxidant capacity
- UV-B increased by ~30 % the glucosinolate content in broccoli and radish sprouts
- Sulforaphane was enhanced by 37.5 % in UV-B-treated broccoli sprouts
- Sulforaphane was increased by 72 % in UV-B-treated radish sprouts
- UV-B treated radish sprouts reported 5-fold higher GL and 60-fold ITC content than broccoli

Brassica olearacea var. *italica* □
Raphanus sativus ○

CTRL
□ ○

UV-C
■ ●

UV-B
■ ●

UV-C+B
■ ●

UVR8
COP1

Responses:
Protein degradation
Transcription

Tryptophan
Indolyl Glucosinolates

Methionine
Aliphatic Glucosinolates

Desulfoglucosinolates

Glucobrassicin
□ ■ ■ ■
○ ● ● ●

4-hydroxy-Glucobrassicin
□ ■ ■ ■
○ ● ● ●

4-methoxy-Glucobrassicin
□ ■ ■ ■*
○ ● ● ●

Neoglucobrassicin
□ ■ ■ ■*
○ ● ● ●

Desulfoglucosinolates

Glucoerucin
□ ■ ■ ■

Dehydroerucin
○ ● ● ●*

Glukoiberin
□ ■ ■ ■
○ ● ● ●

Glucoraphanin
□ ■ ■ ■*

Glucoraphenin
○ ● ● ●*

Progoitrin
□ ■ ■ ■
○ ● ● ●

Total GL content
□ ■ ■ ■
○ ● ● ●

○ > □
5-fold

Isothiocyanates
Sulforaphane
□ ■ ■ ■

Sulforaphene
○ ● ● ●

○ > □
60-fold

Myrosinase

H₂O

Glucose

1 **POSTHARVEST UV-B AND UV-C RADIATION ENHANCED THE**
2 **BIOSYNTHESIS OF GLUCOSINOLATES AND**
3 **ISOTHIOCYANATES IN *BRASSICACEAE* SPROUTS**

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10 **ABSTRACT**

11 The objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of UV lighting (UV-B, UV-C and
12 UV-C + UV-B) as a postharvest abiotic stress in the quality changes of minimally
13 processed *Brassicaceae* sprouts (broccoli and radish) during a shelf-life period of 10 d at
14 4 °C. No UV illumination was used as control (CTRL). The total UV-C doses received
15 were 9 kJ m⁻² (UVC) and 15 kJ m⁻² UV-B (UVB) by applying the 50% of such doses after
16 harvest and on the first day of the shelf-life. Results showed that when UVC was applied,
17 the epiphytic microbial load was reduced up to 1 log CFU g⁻¹ fw. The UVB treatment
18 reported the highest total phenolic content (TPC) and total antioxidant capacity (TAC)
19 after 10 d at 4 °C. In general, both species showed an amelioration effect in the TPC and
20 TAC after UV treatments, which also enhanced the glucosinolate (GL) and the main
21 isothiocyanates (ITC) content. In fact, UVB increased by ~30 % the GL content compared
22 to CTRL samples, which were mostly aliphatic GLs in radish and indolyl GLs in broccoli.
23 As main ITC, sulforaphane content was enhanced by 37.5 % in UVB-treated broccoli
24 sprouts while the sulforaphene content was highly increased by 72 % in radish sprouts.
25 In conclusion, UVB radish sprouts reported 5-fold higher GL content and 60-fold higher
26 biologically ITC content than broccoli sprouts. Therefore, its inclusion in the daily intake
27 is recommended to increase the prevention of chronic inflammatory diseases.

28 **Keywords:** broccoli, radish, *Crucifereae*, fresh-cut, glucoraphanin, sulforaphane.

29 1. INTRODUCTION

30 Plants and vegetables are rich in phytonutrients and fibers, whose intake is necessary and
31 beneficial for the human health. Indeed, regular consumption of plant derivatives has been
32 associated with a reduced risk of chronic diseases, such as cancer, obesity, respiratory or
33 cardiovascular dysfunction (Boeing et al., 2012; Wang et al., 2014). For this reason, new
34 trends in agriculture and fruit and vegetables Industry have focused on the research of
35 new ways to increase the content of bioactive compounds in these ‘super foods’.

36 Cruciferae, like broccoli (*Brassica oleracea* var. *italica*) and radish (*Raphanus sativus*),
37 have become very important due to their high glucosinolate (GL) content (Raiola et al.,
38 2018; Soundararajan and Kim, 2018). As a matter of fact, GLs have been known by their
39 cancer-fighting properties (Raiola et al., 2018; Soundararajan and Kim, 2018) because
40 isothiocyanates (ITC) are synthesized from GLs by the enzyme myrosinase. One of the
41 most important ITC in *Brassica* genus is the sulforaphane in broccoli sprouts (Raiola et
42 al., 2018) and the sulforaphene in radish sprouts, with a double bond formation (Wang et
43 al., 2017) (Figure 1). However, it is not the only product of hydrolysis in cruciferous
44 species, since a high percentage of GLs is converted into sulforaphane nitrile, being
45 sulforaphane the biologically active product (Vanduchova et al., 2019). In addition,
46 activity of the epithiospecific protein (ESP) promotes the formation of the non-bioactive
47 compound sulforaphane nitrile (Castillejo et al., 2018) as well as nitrile-specifier protein
48 (NSP) (Wang et al., 2017). In addition, ITC and indolyl compounds (hydrolytic products
49 of GLs) act as anti-inflammatory compounds, and allow the apoptosis of cancer cells due
50 to their positive role modulating cell cycles (Raiola et al., 2018; Soundararajan and Kim,
51 2018).

52

53 **Figure 1.** Conversion pathway of main glucosinolates to biologically active
 54 isothiocyanates in broccoli and radish sprouts.

55 From a different point of view, sprouts and microgreens are gaining popularity as ‘the
 56 product obtained from the germination of seeds during the first steps of their
 57 development’ (Benincasa et al., 2019). Moreover, the content of nutrients of sprouts are
 58 not only proteins, carbohydrates, fibers, vitamins, minerals. They are also rich in phenolic
 59 compounds, carotenoids, GLs, ITCs.

60 In this line of knowledge, the techniques used in the sector to enhance these bioactive
 61 compounds have been widely investigated in recent years. Particularly, light is a key
 62 factor which directly affects plant growth and synthesis of primary and secondary

63 metabolites, such as phenolic compounds, flavonoids, GLs, and sulforaphane, among
64 others (Zhang et al., 2020). UV lighting (200 – 400 nm) can induce the expression of
65 antioxidant enzymes and the accumulation of anthocyanins, flavonoids, phenolic acids,
66 GLs and ITCs (Dou et al., 2019; Moreira-Rodríguez et al., 2017a; Schreiner et al., 2014).

67 In plants, UV RESPONSE LOCUS 8 (UVR8), as main UV-B receptors, regulate
68 flavonoid biosynthesis, hypocotyl growth inhibition, and leaf cell expansion (Jenkins,
69 2009). Although UV light has been considered harmful for photosynthesis, moderate UV
70 doses have shown positive effects on the biosynthesis of several secondary metabolites,
71 such as flavonoids with photoprotective activity (Guidi et al., 2016). Thus, GL content
72 has been improved in broccoli microgreens (Lu et al., 2018) and broccoli florets
73 (Formica-Oliveira et al. 2017) by postharvest UV-B radiation (280 – 315 nm).

74 Furthermore, although the use of UV-C (200 – 280 nm) has widely shown a high
75 germicidal effect for water treatment, air disinfection, surface decontamination and
76 vegetable preservation (Formica-Oliveira et al. 2017; Tomás-Callejas et al., 2012), recent
77 findings have also shown an enhancement in the biosynthesis of carotenoids and phenolic
78 compounds in tomatoes (Pataro et al., 2015) and *Clerodendrum volubile* (Adetuyi et al.,
79 2020) after low doses of postharvest UV-C treatments. In this way, the biosynthesis of
80 vitamin C and phenolic compounds in acerola fruit has been modulated by low doses of
81 UV-C radiation throughout the increase of the mitochondria activity and reactive oxygen
82 species (ROS) production (Rabelo et al., 2020). In addition, postharvest combination of
83 UV-B and UV-C treatments have also been studied in bimi broccoli (Formica-Oliveira et
84 al. 2017) and peaches (Abdipour et al., 2019) obtaining promising results. Nevertheless,
85 the effect of this light combination has never been simultaneously studied in any sprouts.

86 Therefore, considering the limited knowledge about the postharvest application of UV-B
87 and UV-C light on sprouts, the main objective of the present study was to elucidate the

88 effects of reduced doses of UV postharvest lighting in crucifer sprouts, both the single
89 and combined UV-C and UV-B, **effects** on quality preservation and on the main
90 nutraceutical compounds during a shelf-life period as a minimally processed product.

91 **2. MATERIAL AND METHODS**

92 **2.1. Plant material and sprouting conditions**

93 Broccoli (*Brassica olearacea* var. *italica*) and radish (*Raphanus sativus*) seeds were
94 supplied by Intersemillas S.A. (Valencia, Spain). Four g of broccoli seeds and two g of
95 radish seeds were weighed and sanitized during 10 min with a fungicide (Geoxe 50 WG
96 - Fludioxonil 50 % w/w -; Syngenta). Afterwards, two rinses were conducted with
97 autoclaved distilled water and they were left immersed in water for 18 h in darkness. In a
98 laminar flow hood, the broccoli and radish seeds were arranged in polypropylene (PP)
99 baskets (170 x 120 x 50 mm), using a layer of filter paper moistened with sprayed
100 autoclaved distilled water as a support. To ensure a high relative humidity (RH) the trays
101 were covered with a 40 µm bioriented PP (OPP) film. Broccoli and radish seeds
102 germination was carried out in a growth chamber (Sanyo MLR-350 H, Japan) for 10 d at
103 20 °C and 90 % RH in darkness.

104

2.2. Minimal processing and postharvest UV treatments

After 10 germination days at 20 °C, the sprouts were harvested and washed for 1 min with a sodium hypochlorite solution (150 ppm; 5 °C; pH=6.5) and then rinsed in water for 1 min at 5 °C. A 2 min blotting process on a paper filter sheet was accomplished. The minimally processed sprouts were kept for 10 d at 4 °C in 250 mL PP closed baskets (10 x 8 x 3.5 cm) under 90-95 % RH and normal atmospheric gas partial pressures.

UVB and UVC treatments were applied twice: after harvesting (day 0) and after 24 h on the first day of the shelf-life period at 4 °C. UV treatments were carried out in a reflective stainless-steel chamber as described by Formica-Oliveira et al. (2017b). The radiation chamber was equipped with 12 UV-B unfiltered emitting lamps (TL 40W/01 RS; Philips, Eindhoven, The Netherlands) and 18 UV-C unfiltered emitting lamps (TUV 36W/G36 T8; Philips, Eindhoven, The Netherlands) intercalated above and below the radiation chamber. Closed trays of broccoli and radish sprouts were placed over the net, which was situated in the middle of the chamber between the two lines of lamps at 17.5 cm above and below from them. The UV-B and UV-C lamps were switched on or off depending on the treatment applied. The applied UV-B intensity of $7.99 \pm 0.40 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ was calculated as the mean of 20 readings on each side of the net using a LP 471 UVB (Delta OHM, Italy) radiometer. The applied UV-C intensity of $26.06 \pm 0.37 \text{ W m}^{-2}$ was calculated as the mean of 20 readings on each side of the net using a VLX 254 (Vilber Lourmat, Marne la Vallee, France) radiometer. The light intensities were kept constant, and the applied doses were varied by altering the exposure time at the fixed distance. These doses were applied on day 0 and 1 after harvesting trying to adapt this model to the industry, where sprouts are kept a short period of time before distribution until the pathogenic microbial quality analysis are being conducted. The applied UV treatments were as follows:

- **CTRL:** No UV radiation was used as control.

- 130 - **UVC**: the sprouts received a total effective dose **inside of tray** of 9 kJ m^{-2} UV-C
131 by means of 2 applications of $4.5 \text{ kJ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ (2 min 34 s) after harvesting and after
132 24 h of the postharvest refrigerated period.
- 133 - **UVB**: the sprouts received a total effective dose **inside of tray** of 15 kJ m^{-2} UV-
134 B by means of 2 applications of $7.5 \text{ kJ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ (15 min 39 s) after harvesting and
135 after 24 h of the postharvest refrigerated period.
- 136 - **UVC+B**: the sprouts received the sum of both treatments with a total effective
137 dose **inside of tray** of 9 kJ m^{-2} UV-C + 15 kJ m^{-2} UV-B by means of 2 applications
138 of $4.5 \text{ kJ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ UV-C and $7.5 \text{ kJ m}^{-2} \text{ d}^{-1}$ UV-B applied after harvesting and after
139 24 h of the postharvest refrigerated period.

140 The total dose received was based on our previous unpublished trials and on those
141 recommended by Formica-Oliveira et al. (2017b) in order to obtain maximum
142 phytochemicals accumulation while minimizing heating and evaporation processes
143 during treatment, which may affect the quality of the product.

144 After 1 h of the UV application on days 0 and 1, and on the 4th, 7th, and 10th d of the shelf-
145 life period at 4 °C, samples were frozen at -80 °C until they were freeze-dried (Lyoquest-
146 85, Telstar Technologies, Terrassa, Spain) before the analytical determinations were
147 carried out. In the detailed sampling days, mesophilic, psychrophilic, enterobacteria,
148 yeasts, and moulds growth were analysed following standard methods (Castillejo et al.,
149 2016; Martínez-Hernández et al., 2013). All microbial counts were reported as log colony
150 forming units per gram of product ($\log \text{ CFU g}^{-1}$). Three **replicates** per treatment were
151 analysed on each sampling day.

152 **2.3. Extraction of phenolic compounds**

153 Twenty-five mg of freeze-dried sprouts were placed in tubes and 3 mL MeOH:H₂O (80:20,
154 v/v) were added. The extraction was carried out in an orbital shaker (Stuart, Stone, UK)

155 where the samples were vigorously shaken for 1 h in darkness at 4 °C. The methanolic
156 extracts were centrifuged at 3220 g for 10 min at 4 °C. The supernatant was collected and
157 kept at -80 °C until analysis of Total Phenolic Content (TPC) and Total Antioxidant
158 Capacity (TAC).

159 **2.4. Total phenolic content**

160 TPC was determined as previously described by Castillejo et al. (2021). Briefly, 19 µL
161 sample extract were placed on a 96-well plate (Greiner Bio-One; Frickenhausen, Germany)
162 and 29 µL of 1 mol L⁻¹ Folin–Ciocalteu reagent were added. After 3 min incubation in
163 darkness, 192 µL of 0.4 % Na₂CO₃ 2 % NaOH were added. The absorbance was measured
164 at 750 nm using a microplate reader (Tecan Infinite M200, Männedorf, Switzerland) after
165 1 h incubation in darkness. The TPC was expressed as g chlorogenic acid equivalents
166 (CAE) kg⁻¹ dry weight (dw). Each sample was analysed in triplicate.

167 **2.5. Total antioxidant capacity**

168 Total antioxidant capacity was directly related to the ability to scavenge the 2,2-diphenyl-
169 1-picrilhidrazilo (DPPH) free radical. DPPH assay was performed following the method
170 described by Martínez-Zamora et al. (2021). For that, 194 µL of DPPH (0.7 mM) solution
171 were added to 21 µL of sprout extract. The mixture was incubated for 30 min in darkness.
172 The TAC by DPPH was measured by changes in absorbance at 515 nm. Obtained data were
173 expressed as g of Trolox equivalents (TE) kg⁻¹ dw. Each sample was analysed in triplicate.

174 **2.6. Extraction and analysis of Glucosinolates**

175 Extraction and analysis of GLs content was carried out following the method described by
176 Moreira-Rodríguez et al. (2017b). Briefly, 10 mL of ethanol/water (70:30, v/v) previously
177 heated at 70 °C in a bath were added to sprouts powder (0.2 ± 0.01 g) followed by the
178 addition of 50 µL of 3 mM sinigrin as internal standard. To ensure myrosinase inactivation,
179 samples were incubated at 70 °C for 30 min and vortexed at 0, 10, and 20 min. The extracts

180 were removed from the water bath, rapidly cooled on an ice bath, and centrifuged at 18,000
181 g for 10 min at 4 °C (L-90K Ultracentrifuge Beckman Coulter, rotor type 45 70Ti). The
182 clarified extract (supernatant) was recovered for GLs analysis. Immediately after the
183 extraction, GLs were desulphated and purified using disposable polypropylene columns
184 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). Columns were prepared by adding 0.5
185 mL of MilliQ water, followed by 0.5 mL of Sephadex A-25 and 0.5 mL of MilliQ water.
186 Then, 3 mL of clarified ethanolic extract were added into a prepared column and allowed
187 to drip through slowly. Columns were washed with 2 × 0.5 mL of MilliQ water followed
188 by 2 × 0.5 mL of 0.02 M sodium acetate. Purified sulfatase (75 µL) was added to each
189 sample and left at room temperature overnight (16 h). Desulfoglucosinolates were eluted
190 with a total of 1.25 mL of water and kept at -80 °C until UHPLC analysis. Analysis and
191 identification of GLs were conducted according to Moreira-Rodríguez et al. (2017b). For
192 that, an Ultra High Performance Liquid Chromatography (UHPLC) instrument (Shimadzu,
193 Kyoto, Japan) equipped with a DGU-20A degasser, LC-30AD quaternary pump, SIL-
194 30AC autosampler, CTO-10AS column heater, and SPDM-20A photodiode array detector
195 was used. Chromatographic analyses were carried out into a Gemini C18 column (250 mm
196 x 4.6 mm, 5 µm particle size; Phenomenex, Torrance CA, USA). Separation of
197 desulfoglucosinolates in the UHPLC system was achieved using water (phase A) and
198 acetonitrile (phase B) as mobile phases with a flow rate of 1.5 mL min⁻¹ and a gradient of
199 0/100, 28/80, 30/100 (min/% phase A) with an injection volume of 20 µL.
200 Desulfoglucosinolates were detected at 227 nm and identified compounds are shown in
201 **Figure 4**. The results were expressed as g kg⁻¹ dw. Each sample was extracted and analysed
202 in triplicate.

203 **2.7. Extraction and analysis of isothiocyanates**

204 Sulforaphane content was analysed according to Martínez-Hernández et al. (2019). For that,
205 0.25 g of freeze-dried sprouts were mixed with 5 mL of milliQ water (pH=6) and incubated
206 at 45 °C for 2 h to allow glucoraphanin conversion to sulforaphane. Then, 25 mL MTBE
207 were added and sonicated for 1 min. This mixture was dewatered using 5.5 g of sodium
208 sulphate and filtered through Whatman 41 filter papers. The collected extract was passed
209 through an activated (3 mL MTBE + 3 mL ethyl acetate + 3 mL air) SI-1 silica cartridge
210 (Phenomenex, Torrance, CA, USA) and the eluent was discarded. After that, sulforaphane
211 was eluted with 2 mL of methanol and evaporated in a rotary evaporator at 45 °C. The final
212 dry residue was resuspended in 1 mL acetonitrile and filtered (0.45 µm).

213 Sulforaphane extracts were analysed in an UHPLC (Shimadzu, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with
214 a DGU-20A degasser, LC-30AD quaternary pump, SIL-30AC autosampler, CTO-10AS
215 column heater, and SPDM-20A photodiode array detector was used. Chromatographic
216 analyses were carried out into a Gemini C18 column (250 mm x 4.6 mm, 5 µm particle
217 size; Phenomenex, Torrance CA, USA). For that, the mobile phases used were 20 mmol L⁻¹
218 ammonium formate (phase A) and acetonitrile (phase B). The injection volume was 5 µL
219 (draw speed of 50 µL min⁻¹), flow rate 0.6 mL min⁻¹, temperature at 25 °C and detection
220 wavelength at 196 nm. Sulforaphane was quantified using DL-sulforaphane standard
221 (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) and results were expressed as g kg⁻¹ dw. Each sample
222 was analysed in triplicate.

223 2.8. Statistical analyses

224 The experiment was a two-factor (treatment × time) design subjected to analysis of variance
225 (ANOVA) using Statgraphics Plus software (v. 5.1. Statpoint Technologies. Inc.
226 Warrenton. VA. USA). Statistical significance was assessed at the level $p < 0.05$, and
227 Tukey's multiple range test was used to separate means.

228 3. RESULTS

229 **3.1. Characterization**

230 The morphological characteristics of 10-d broccoli (*Brassica olearacea* var. *italica*) and
 231 radish (*Raphanus sativus*) sprouts are shown in Table 1. The broccoli sprout length
 232 (cotyledon + hypocotyl + root) was 6.21 ± 0.67 cm, and the radish sprout length was 6.71
 233 ± 0.67 cm. Radish sprouts presented a thicker hypocotyl and they were yellowish in
 234 colour, while broccoli sprouts presented smaller and greener leaves. Furthermore, fresh
 235 weight/dry weight (FW/DW) ratio was lower in radish sprouts, which means that dry
 236 mass of broccoli sprouts was lower.

237 **Table 1.** Morphological characteristics of broccoli and radish sprouts harvested after 10
 238 germination days at 20 °C and 90 % RH under Darkness conditions.

	Broccoli sprouts <i>Brassica olearacea</i> var. <i>italica</i>	Radish sprouts <i>Raphanus sativus</i>
Cotyledon (cm)	0.77 ± 0.02	
Hypocotyl (cm)	3.85 ± 0.39	3.19 ± 0.08
Diameter (cm)	0.09 ± 0.00	0.13 ± 0.00
Root (cm)	1.93 ± 0.25	2.75 ± 0.57
FW/DW	7.6	5.8

239 The morphological characteristics were determined using the ImageJ program (Wayne Rasband, Maryland, USA).
 240 n=30. FW/DW: Fresh weight/Dry weight ratio; n=70

241 The epiphytic microflora load of broccoli sprouts after harvesting was 8.7 ± 0.0 cfu g⁻¹
 242 fw for mesophilic microorganisms, 8.2 ± 0.0 cfu g⁻¹ fw for psychrophilic microorganisms,
 243 5.6 ± 0.1 cfu g⁻¹ fw for enterobacteria, and 6.3 ± 0.0 cfu g⁻¹ fw for moulds and yeast (Table
 244 S1).

245 In a similar way, on the processing day, the mesophilic load of radish sprouts was $8.6 \pm$
 246 0.0 cfu g⁻¹ fw, whereas the psychrophilic count was 8.3 ± 0.1 cfu g⁻¹ fw. As well, radish
 247 sprouts had 5.7 ± 0.1 cfu enterobacteria g⁻¹ fw and 5.1 ± 0.1 cfu moulds and yeast g⁻¹ fw,

248 which was also maintained throughout the refrigerated period with no significant
249 differences (Table S2).

250 Accordingly, UV-C doses applied on day 0 and 1 of the refrigerated storage period at 4
251 °C reduced the microbial load (mesophilic, psychrophilic, enterobacteria, moulds, and
252 yeast) by approximately 0.5 and 1 log CFU g⁻¹ fw compared to CTRL sprouts in both
253 cruciferous species, which was only observed immediately after UV treatment. The
254 simultaneous application of UVC and UVB also reduced the microbial load of
255 mesophilic bacteria and moulds and yeasts by 0.5 log CFU g⁻¹ fw in comparison with
256 CTRL sprouts on application days.

257 3.2. Total phenolic content

258 The germination process of radish seeds during 10 d at 20 °C naturally increased the TPC
259 by 108 % in CTRL sprouts while its content was highly increased in UVC, UVB, and
260 UVC+B treated samples by 125, 160, and 187 %, respectively (Figure 2).

261 The evolution of TPC during storage at 4 °C was similar in all treatments. During the first
262 4 d of storage, the TPC was maintained at similar values, however, an increase in TPC
263 was observed after the 7th d of storage. Particularly, after the first UV application on day
264 0, UVB and UVC+B treatments significantly increased the TPC by 25 and 38 %, respectively,
265 compared to the CTRL. This fact was also observed in UVC+B treated
266 radish sprouts when the second UV application was performed after 1 d at 4°C. The UVC
267 and UVC+B treatments increased the TPC after 4 d at 4 °C compared to CTRL and again
268 UVC+B also reported an increase after the shelf-life period of 10 d at 4 °C regarding
269 CTRL.

270 The same tendency was observed in the broccoli model. The TPC of broccoli sprouts
271 increased during germination at 20 °C. Indeed, the TPC increased by 255, 306, 298, and

272 295 % in CTRL, UVC, UVB, and UVC+B treatments compared to broccoli seed,
273 respectively. In this case, UVC showed the highest values of TPC on day 0 and 1 after
274 harvesting, while UVB showed highest TPC on day 10 at 4 °C. Although no differences
275 were observed after UV treatments, a clear tendency to enhance the TPC have been also
276 found in broccoli sprouts on days 0, 1, and 10 of the refrigerated storage.

277

278

279 **Figure 2.** Total phenolic content of UV treated broccoli (A) and radish (B) sprouts stored for 10 d at 4 °C. T: treatment; t: time. n.s.: no
 280 significant differences. ***: P < 0.001. *: significant differences regarding CTRL samples.

281

282 3.3. Total antioxidant capacity

283 From a general point of view, the TAC of the studied **broccoli** sprouts increased during
284 germination, but when they **reached** the optimal vegetative growth as a ready to eat sprout,
285 their TAC was maintained during the postharvest storage at 4 °C (**Figure 3**). **However, for**
286 **radish sprouts, the TAC increased up to 7 d at 4°C and then was maintained up to end of**
287 **storage (10 d at 4 °C).**

288 The initial TAC of 10-d CTRL radish sprouts was 7.5 g TE kg⁻¹ dw, which was increased
289 after the first UV application by 28, 55 and 72 % in UVC, UVB and UVC+B treatments,
290 respectively. Although UVC stood out after both UV applications, its effect was not
291 maintained throughout the 10 d at 4 °C. Indeed, UVB **had** higher **TAC** throughout the
292 postharvest period, while UVC+B stood out on day 4. As it happened with the TPC
293 (**Figure 2**), the TAC increased after 7 d at 4 °C in all treatments.

294 The germination process during 10 d at 20 °C increased by 208 % the initial TAC in
295 broccoli seeds (6.0 g TE kg⁻¹ dw). In this case, the **positive** effect of the UV treatments
296 was not observed after the UV applications (**at harvest – 0 d – and on the first day of**
297 **refrigerated storage – 1 d –**). The TAC of UV-untreated broccoli sprouts was maintained
298 in the same range throughout the storage period at 4 °C. However, on day 7, the TAC
299 increased by 40 % in UVB and UVC+B treatments compared to CTRL, while, on day 10,
300 an increase of 28 % was found in all UV treatments regarding CTRL.

301

302

303

304 **Figure 3.** Total antioxidant capacity measured by DPPH of UV treated broccoli (A) and radish (B) sprouts stored for 10 d at 4 °C. T: treatment; t:
 305 time. ***: P < 0.001. *: significant differences regarding CTRL samples.

306

307 **3.4. Glucosinolate content**

308 According to U-HPLC chromatograms, the identified aliphatic GLs derived from alanine,
309 leucine, isoleucine, methionine, or valine were (1) Glucoiberin, (2) Progoitrin, (3)
310 Glucoraphanin / Glucoraphenin, and (5) Glucoerucin / Dehydroerucin, for broccoli /
311 radish sprouts, respectively. Meanwhile, indoyl GLs derived from tryptophan found were
312 (4) 4-Hydroxy-glucobrassicin, (6) Glucobrassicin, (7) 4-Methoxy-glucobrassicin, and (8)
313 Neoglucobrassicin (Figure 4).

314 The amount of these eight GLs for broccoli and radish sprouts is shown in Table 2 and
315 Table 3, respectively. The total GL content of both *Brassicaceae* sprouts is presented in
316 Figure 5.

317

318 **Figure 4.** U-HPLC chromatograms (shown at 227 nm) of identified glucosinolates from ethanol/water (70:30, v/v) extracts of broccoli and radish
 319 seeds and sprouts treated with UV (CTRL, UVB, UVC, and UVC+B) during 10 d stored at 4 °C. Identified peaks in broccoli sprouts (A) are: (1)
 320 Glucoiberin, (2) Progoitrin, (3) Glucoraphenin, (4) 4-hydroxy-glucobrassicin, (5) Glucoerucin, (6) Glucobrassicin, (7) 4-methoxy-glucobrassicin,
 321 and (8) Neoglucobrassicin. Identified peaks in radish sprouts (B) are: (1) Glucoiberin, (2) Progoitrin, (3) Glucoraphenin, (4) 4-hydroxy-
 322 glucobrassicin, (5) Dehydroerucin, (6) Glucobrassicin, (7) 4-methoxy-glucobrassicin, and (8) Neoglucobrassicin.

323 **Table 2.** Glucosinolate content (g kg⁻¹ dw) of UV treated broccoli sprouts during a shelf-life period of 10 d at 4 °C.

<i>Treatment</i>	<i>Day of analysis</i>	<i>Glucobrassicin</i>	<i>Progoitrin</i>	<i>Glucoraphanin</i>	<i>4-hydroxy-glucobrassicin</i>	<i>Glucorucin</i>	<i>Glucobrassicin</i>	<i>4-methoxy-glucobrassicin</i>	<i>Neoglucobrassicin</i>
	Seed	6.56 ± 0.99 ^{a/a/a/a}	0.12 ± 0.05 ^{b/b/b/b}	16.39 ± 1.27 ^{a/a/a/a}	17.17 ± 1.22 ^{a/a/a/a}	8.69 ± 0.78 ^{a/a/a/a}	0.27 ± 0.05 ^{b/c/d/b}	0.36 ± 0.04 ^{c/c/c/d}	0.58 ± 0.07 ^{e/c/d/e}
CTRL	0	2.75 ± 0.23 ^b	0.79 ± 0.17 ^a	6.92 ± 1.08 ^b	6.82 ± 1.04 ^b	5.42 ± 0.06 ^b	2.37 ± 0.45 ^a	9.19 ± 0.61 ^{Bab}	6.07 ± 0.39 ^{Dbc}
	1	2.56 ± 0.32 ^b	0.79 ± 0.17 ^a	6.26 ± 0.18 ^{Cb}	4.10 ± 0.63 ^c	4.71 ± 0.46 ^{Cbc}	2.36 ± 0.31 ^a	7.81 ± 0.02 ^{Cb}	6.59 ± 0.79 ^{Ab}
	4	2.75 ± 0.18 ^{ABb}	0.72 ± 0.03 ^a	6.59 ± 0.64 ^{ABb}	3.02 ± 0.23 ^{Cc}	4.29 ± 0.19 ^{Bbc}	1.89 ± 0.31 ^{Ba}	8.97 ± 0.28 ^{Bab}	4.37 ± 0.07 ^{Dd}
	7	2.73 ± 0.26 ^{Bb}	0.86 ± 0.05 ^a	7.09 ± 1.06 ^b	4.22 ± 0.61 ^{Bc}	3.98 ± 0.62 ^{Bc}	2.16 ± 0.27 ^{Ca}	10.52 ± 0.76 ^{Ba}	4.93 ± 0.54 ^{Ccd}
	10	2.61 ± 0.09 ^{ABb}	0.86 ± 0.07 ^a	5.61 ± 0.33 ^{ABb}	4.09 ± 0.22 ^c	4.07 ± 0.56 ^{bc}	2.26 ± 0.04 ^{Ba}	10.39 ± 1.22 ^{Ca}	7.89 ± 0.28 ^{Ca}
UVC	0	2.58 ± 0.17 ^b	0.79 ± 0.18 ^a	6.81 ± 1.05 ^b	6.27 ± 0.73 ^b	4.98 ± 0.54 ^b	2.22 ± 0.10 ^b	7.27 ± 0.50 ^{Cb}	7.84 ± 0.65 ^{Ca}
	1	3.23 ± 0.16 ^b	0.83 ± 0.19 ^a	7.97 ± 0.34 ^{Bb}	4.89 ± 1.09 ^{bc}	5.68 ± 0.41 ^{Bb}	2.26 ± 0.50 ^b	8.02 ± 0.04 ^{Cb}	6.05 ± 0.72 ^{ABb}
	4	2.67 ± 0.21 ^{ABb}	0.82 ± 0.12 ^a	6.80 ± 0.38 ^{ABb}	3.49 ± 0.06 ^{BCc}	5.05 ± 0.58 ^{ABb}	2.50 ± 0.28 ^{ABab}	8.03 ± 0.89 ^{Bb}	5.52 ± 0.06 ^{Cb}
	7	3.40 ± 0.12 ^{Ab}	0.87 ± 0.06 ^a	8.02 ± 0.25 ^b	5.64 ± 0.67 ^{ABbc}	5.90 ± 0.12 ^{Ab}	3.09 ± 0.03 ^{Ba}	11.44 ± 0.40 ^{Ba}	7.88 ± 0.17 ^{Ba}
	10	3.09 ± 0.36 ^{Ab}	1.01 ± 0.12 ^a	7.64 ± 1.31 ^{Ab}	4.53 ± 0.43 ^{bc}	5.19 ± 0.55 ^b	2.70 ± 0.10 ^{Aab}	12.24 ± 0.18 ^{Ba}	7.68 ± 0.23 ^{Ca}
UVB	0	2.64 ± 0.10 ^b	0.83 ± 0.17 ^a	6.42 ± 0.48 ^c	7.61 ± 1.48 ^b	5.11 ± 0.43 ^{cd}	2.51 ± 0.22 ^{bc}	11.34 ± 0.39 ^{Ab}	11.21 ± 0.06 ^{Aab}
	1	3.28 ± 0.47 ^b	0.69 ± 0.14 ^a	9.49 ± 0.20 ^{Ab}	4.68 ± 1.27 ^c	6.86 ± 0.14 ^{Ab}	2.11 ± 0.24 ^c	10.22 ± 0.22 ^{Ab}	6.29 ± 0.83 ^{ABc}
	4	3.20 ± 0.18 ^{Ab}	0.86 ± 0.08 ^a	7.65 ± 0.43 ^{Abc}	4.85 ± 0.11 ^{Abc}	5.93 ± 0.27 ^{Abc}	2.73 ± 0.30 ^{Ab}	11.14 ± 0.07 ^{Ab}	10.13 ± 0.82 ^{Ab}
	7	3.35 ± 0.27 ^{Ab}	0.95 ± 0.08 ^a	7.40 ± 0.41 ^c	6.39 ± 1.09 ^{Abc}	5.74 ± 0.05 ^{Abcd}	3.62 ± 0.01 ^{Aa}	15.11 ± 1.14 ^{Aa}	10.04 ± 1.19 ^{Ab}
	10	2.74 ± 0.43 ^{ABb}	0.97 ± 0.13 ^a	6.52 ± 0.79 ^{ABc}	4.18 ± 0.23 ^c	4.63 ± 0.41 ^d	3.02 ± 0.25 ^{Ab}	15.63 ± 0.08 ^{Aa}	12.28 ± 0.06 ^{Aa}
UVC+B	0	2.86 ± 0.54 ^{bc}	0.75 ± 0.15 ^a	6.91 ± 1.57 ^{bc}	4.85 ± 1.34 ^b	5.05 ± 0.32 ^b	2.02 ± 0.48 ^a	7.07 ± 0.09 ^{Cc}	9.81 ± 0.18 ^{Ba}
	1	2.50 ± 0.07 ^{bc}	0.72 ± 0.03 ^a	5.74 ± 0.26 ^{Cbc}	2.84 ± 0.49 ^b	4.02 ± 0.33 ^{Cb}	1.62 ± 0.25 ^a	8.78 ± 0.15 ^{Bb}	4.76 ± 0.08 ^{Bd}
	4	2.65 ± 0.24 ^{Bbc}	0.80 ± 0.02 ^a	5.95 ± 0.52 ^{Bbc}	4.62 ± 0.86 ^{ABb}	4.90 ± 0.50 ^{ABb}	2.00 ± 0.29 ^{ABa}	8.55 ± 0.12 ^{Bb}	6.71 ± 0.10 ^{Bc}
	7	3.38 ± 0.12 ^{Ab}	0.96 ± 0.10 ^a	7.82 ± 1.11 ^b	4.18 ± 0.58 ^{Bb}	5.30 ± 0.66 ^{Ab}	1.53 ± 0.02 ^{Da}	9.85 ± 0.10 ^{Ba}	5.89 ± 0.89 ^{BCc}
	10	1.99 ± 0.20 ^{Bc}	0.98 ± 0.17 ^a	4.93 ± 0.48 ^{Bc}	3.61 ± 0.78 ^b	4.00 ± 0.29 ^b	1.49 ± 0.01 ^{Ca}	6.99 ± 0.13 ^{Dc}	8.77 ± 0.07 ^{Bb}

324 Different capital letters denote significant differences (p<0.05) among different treatments for the same sampling time. Different lowercase letters denote significant differences

325 (p<0.05) among different sampling times for the same treatment. Absence of letters indicates that there are no significant differences (p<0.05).

327 **Table 3.** Glucosinolate content (g kg⁻¹ dw) of UV treated radish sprouts during a shelf-life period of 10 d at 4 °C.

<i>Treatment</i>	<i>Day of analysis</i>	<i>Glucoiberin</i>	<i>Progoitrin</i>	<i>Glucoraphenin</i>	<i>4-hydroxy-glucobrassicin</i>	<i>Dehydroerucin</i>	<i>Glucobrassicin</i>	<i>4-methoxy-glucobrassicin</i>	<i>Neoglucobrassicin</i>
	Seed	0.28 ± 0.01 ab/c/c/b	0.65 ± 0.02 ^{b/b/c/c}	197.6 ± 9.9 ^{a/a/a/a}	26.4 ± 4.4 ^{a/a/a/a}	12 ± 1 ^{c/c/c/b}	0.39 ± 0.04 ^{d/c/b/b}	3.0 ± 0.0 ^{d/d/d/c}	50.55 ± 4.97 ^{a/a/a/a}
CTRL	0	0.24 ± 0.01 ^{Bb}	0.71 ± 0.13 ^{ab}	46.7 ± 0.8 ^{Bb}	14.3 ± 4.1 ^b	96 ± 6 ^{Cb}	1.01 ± 0.09 ^{ab}	7.9 ± 0.5 ^{Bc}	0.36 ± 0.06 ^{Bc}
	1	0.40 ± 0.03 ^{Ba}	0.69 ± 0.03 ^{Bb}	40.5 ± 8.9 ^b	13.1 ± 1.5 ^{ABb}	102 ± 5 ^{Cab}	0.72 ± 0.01 ^{Bc}	9.7 ± 0.2 ^{Bc}	4.18 ± 0.87 ^{bc}
	4	0.39 ± 0.06 ^{Ba}	1.05 ± 0.07 ^a	46.8 ± 6.4 ^{Cb}	14.5 ± 1.6 ^b	111 ± 6 ^{Ba}	0.96 ± 0.01 ^{ab}	14.5 ± 0.5 ^b	6.11 ± 0.38 ^b
	7	0.37 ± 0.08 ^a	0.94 ± 0.11 ^{ab}	52.5 ± 3.7 ^b	13.6 ± 2.4 ^b	109 ± 2 ^{Ba}	1.20 ± 0.01 ^a	15.4 ± 0.2 ^{Cab}	1.37 ± 0.19 ^{Bbc}
	10	0.39 ± 0.03 ^{Ba}	0.89 ± 0.24 ^{ab}	52.1 ± 0.1 ^{Bb}	14.6 ± 0.0 ^b	109 ± 1 ^{Ba}	1.20 ± 0.31 ^a	16.9 ± 1.5 ^{Ca}	1.25 ± 0.21 ^{bc}
UVC	0	0.33 ± 0.04 ^{ABc}	0.72 ± 0.13 ^b	77.8 ± 15.3 ^{Ab}	17.2 ± 2.8 ^b	142 ± 8 ^{ABa}	0.84 ± 0.09 ^{abc}	9.0 ± 2.2 ^{ABc}	1.13 ± 0.18 ^{Bb}
	1	0.38 ± 0.01 ^{Bbc}	1.09 ± 0.14 ^{Aa}	49.1 ± 12.9 ^c	13.1 ± 2.3 ^{ABb}	129 ± 8 ^{Bab}	0.77 ± 0.02 ^{ABbc}	8.3 ± 1.2 ^{Bc}	4.69 ± 1.09 ^b
	4	0.50 ± 0.03 ^{ABa}	1.27 ± 0.09 ^a	87.4 ± 6.2 ^{Ab}	16.9 ± 0.8 ^b	114 ± 4 ^{Bb}	1.31 ± 0.36 ^a	15.6 ± 1.0 ^b	6.56 ± 0.64 ^b
	7	0.45 ± 0.00 ^{ab}	1.07 ± 0.12 ^a	69.8 ± 6.8 ^{bc}	15.7 ± 1.3 ^b	124 ± 8 ^{Bab}	1.19 ± 0.18 ^{ab}	17.4 ± 0.5 ^{Bb}	3.51 ± 0.72 ^{Ab}
	10	0.47 ± 0.07 ^{ABab}	1.05 ± 0.06 ^a	65.0 ± 4.6 ^{Bbc}	16.1 ± 2.0 ^b	133 ± 10 ^{ABab}	1.06 ± 0.10 ^{ab}	20.8 ± 0.9 ^{Ba}	1.57 ± 0.75 ^b
UVB	0	0.37 ± 0.05 ^{Abc}	0.82 ± 0.13 ^{bc}	64.5 ± 6.7 ^{ABbc}	17.2 ± 1.2 ^b	170 ± 19 ^{Aa}	0.73 ± 0.26 ^b	8.8 ± 1.5 ^{Bc}	3.95 ± 0.32 ^{Ab}
	1	0.53 ± 0.12 ^{ABab}	1.01 ± 0.07 ^{Aab}	60.7 ± 8.6 ^c	12.1 ± 2.5 ^{Bb}	159 ± 6 ^{Aab}	0.69 ± 0.12 ^{Bb}	9.8 ± 0.3 ^{Bc}	3.76 ± 0.61 ^b
	4	0.60 ± 0.10 ^{Aa}	1.35 ± 0.20 ^a	86.7 ± 12.3 ^{Ab}	15.4 ± 1.5 ^b	152 ± 10 ^{Aab}	1.15 ± 0.14 ^a	18.2 ± 1.6 ^b	6.62 ± 1.07 ^b
	7	0.45 ± 0.01 ^{abc}	1.02 ± 0.20 ^{ab}	64.4 ± 9.1 ^{bc}	12.3 ± 0.4 ^b	168 ± 0 ^{Aa}	1.20 ± 0.01 ^a	25.3 ± 0.0 ^{Aa}	0.99 ± 0.04 ^{Bb}
	10	0.58 ± 0.10 ^{Aab}	1.20 ± 0.06 ^a	86.7 ± 5.4 ^{Ab}	16.4 ± 2.9 ^b	136 ± 16 ^{Ab}	1.24 ± 0.11 ^a	27.5 ± 1.2 ^{Aa}	1.51 ± 0.12 ^b
UVC+B	0	0.41 ± 0.05 ^{Ab}	0.75 ± 0.06 ^{bc}	65.9 ± 4.6 ^{ABb}	16.3 ± 1.4 ^b	139 ± 3 ^{Ba}	0.81 ± 0.28 ^{ab}	12.8 ± 1.2 ^{Ab}	3.86 ± 0.92 ^{Ab}
	1	0.65 ± 0.11 ^{Aa}	1.02 ± 0.12 ^{Aab}	58.7 ± 2.1 ^b	18.2 ± 2.7 ^{Ab}	132 ± 9 ^{Ba}	1.10 ± 0.23 ^{Aa}	12.4 ± 1.3 ^{Ab}	4.31 ± 0.33 ^b
	4	0.45 ± 0.10 ^{ABb}	1.13 ± 0.07 ^a	67.3 ± 1.1 ^{Bb}	17.4 ± 1.8 ^b	126 ± 19 ^{ABa}	1.15 ± 0.29 ^a	15.8 ± 3.0 ^b	6.77 ± 0.42 ^b
	7	0.45 ± 0.06 ^b	0.93 ± 0.09 ^{abc}	57.4 ± 2.3 ^b	16.8 ± 3.0 ^b	120 ± 9 ^{Ba}	1.04 ± 0.22 ^a	15.6 ± 1.2 ^b	2.42 ± 0.16 ^{ABb}
	10	0.48 ± 0.07 ^{ABab}	1.02 ± 0.18 ^{ab}	59.0 ± 8.6 ^{Bb}	11.5 ± 1.6 ^b	116 ± 1 ^{ABa}	0.94 ± 0.14 ^{ab}	23.2 ± 2.1 ^{Ba}	1.02 ± 0.09 ^b

328 Different capital letters denote significant differences (p<0.05) among different treatments for the same sampling time. Different lowercase letters denote significant differences

329 (p<0.05) among different sampling times for the same treatment. Absence of letters indicates that there are no significant differences (p<0.05).

330

331 **Figure 5.** Total glucosinolates of UV treated broccoli (A) and radish (B) sprouts stored for 10 d at 4 °C. T: treatment; t: time. ***: P < 0.001. *:
 332 significant differences regarding CTRL samples.

333

334 Aliphatic GLs accounted the 72 % of the total in the radish seed, increasing up to 85 %
335 in the radish sprouts. The predominant GL found was Dehydroerucin (also known as
336 Glucoraphasatin), reporting 57 % of total, but only a 4 % in the seed. As appreciated in
337 Table 3, the radish seeds were rich in Glucoraphenin, with a 68 % of total. Glucoraphenin
338 was the second most common GL in radish sprouts, representing a 27 % of total.

339 The initial total GL content was $291 \text{ g kg}^{-1} \text{ dw}$ in the radish seed, which decreased by 58
340 % after 10 d of sprouting at 20 °C (CTRL). **The GL content accounted a 16.7 % of dry**
341 **matter of 10-day radish sprouts.** The UV application stimulated the total GL content while
342 preserving the content initially present in the seed. After the first UV dose, an increase of
343 33, 37 and 30 % was observed in UVC, UVB and UVC+B, respectively, compared to
344 CTRL. After that, the second UV application increased by 31 and 25 % the total GL
345 content in the UVB and UVC+B radish sprouts, respectively. The residual effect of the
346 UV application was positively maintained during 10 d at 4 °C. UVB treatment presented
347 the highest concentration of total GLs during the shelf-life period. UVC+B treatment did
348 not have a better effect, and no differences were observed with the other UV treated
349 sprouts. **On** days 7 and 10 the combination of both UV lightings considerably reduced the
350 total GL content without differences compared to CTRL radish sprouts.

351 In the case of broccoli seed, the aliphatic GLs were also the major group found,
352 accounting for 63 % of the total content. However, this GL group was reduced by
353 germination representing only the 39 % after 10 sprouting days. At this moment, the
354 predominant GL was 4-Methoxy-glucobrassicin in broccoli sprouts, followed by
355 Neoglucobrassicin and Glucoraphenin. Broccoli seeds were rich in 4-Hydroxy-
356 glucobrassicin and Glucoraphenin, with a 33 and 34 % of the total content, respectively
357 (Table 2).

358 The initial concentration of total GLs in broccoli seed was 50.1 g kg⁻¹ dw, which followed
359 the same tendency previously described for radish sprouts. The application of UVB had
360 an hormetic effect on the biosynthesis of GLs and these levels were maintained like those
361 reported for seeds. On the minimal processing day, the total GL content was 40.3 g kg⁻¹
362 dw in CTRL broccoli sprouts. After this moment, when light stressors were applied, UVB
363 reported an increase of 18 % after the first UV application, reaching an increase of 44 %
364 on the 7th d. The UVC and UVC+B treatments did not positively affect to the GLs content.
365 In fact, the UVC+B treatment reported similar amounts to CTRL sprouts.

366 Although, the UV treatments had a positive effect on GL content of both studied models,
367 radish sprouts presented 5-fold more GLs content than broccoli sprouts (Figure 5). The
368 total GL content was markedly reduced after the sprouting period and then maintained
369 throughout the shelf-life period in CTRL sprouts. UVB lighting was able to induce the
370 biosynthesis of GLs to a similar amount to that found in seeds and maintained it
371 throughout the postharvest period.

372 **3.5. Isothiocyanate content**

373 According to results found in broccoli sprouts, at harvest, CTRL samples reported 0.05 g
374 kg⁻¹ dw of sulforaphane, as biologically active compound, accounting the 8 % of the total
375 sulforaphane content (Table 4). After the first UV application, no differences were
376 observed among treatments. However, the second UVB and UVC+B application
377 increased by 37.5 % the biologically active sulforaphane content regarding CTRL
378 samples, which can be due to the increase in the glucoraphanin content of UVB-treated
379 sprouts by 51 %. This increase was not observed in UVC+B treatment. The residual effect
380 of the UVB treatment on sulforaphane was not observed from day 4, this is corroborated
381 by the fact that the glucoraphanin compound remained constant in those days. In the case

382 of UV-untreated 10-d broccoli sprouts, only the 0.8 % of the glucoraphanin compound
383 was converted into sulforaphane.

384 Concerning radish sprouts, around 70 % of the total sulforaphane content corresponded
385 to the sulforaphene compound, only 30 % corresponded to its nitrile form, which is
386 biologically inactive. While the nitrile form was not affected by the germination, the
387 sulforaphene was increased 26-fold compared to the seeds content (Table 4).

388 CTRL radish sprouts reported 2.65 g kg⁻¹ dw of sulforaphene at harvest. However, the
389 first application of UVC and UVB increased by 57 and 72 %, respectively, the
390 sulforaphene content regarding CTRL. In contrast, after the second UVC+B application,
391 the sulforaphene content increased by 38 % compared to CTRL (day 1). Also, the UVB
392 and UVC+B treatments in radish sprouts kept in a similar amount the sulforaphene
393 content throughout the storage period at 4 °C.

394 **In summary, UV treatments were good as abiotic elicitors, increasing isothiocyanate**
395 **content in the case of both species.**

396 **Table 4.** Sulforaphane content (g kg⁻¹ dw) of UV treated broccoli and radish sprouts during a shelf-life period of 10 d at 4 °C.

<i>Treatment</i>	Day of analysis	Broccoli			Radish		
		Sulforaphane nitrile	Sulforaphane	Total Sulforaphane	Sulforaphene nitrile	Sulforaphene	Total Sulforaphene
	Seed	0.53 ± 0.10 ^{bc/c/b/bc}	0.06 ± 0.01 ^{ab/a/b/b}	0.59 ± 0.11 ^{b/c/e/bc}	0.71 ± 0.25 ^{c/c/c/d}	0.10 ± 0.03 ^{b/b/c/b}	0.81 ± 0.28 ^{b/b/c/c}
CTRL	0	0.55 ± 0.16 ^{Bbc}	0.05 ± 0.01 ^{ABbc}	0.60 ± 0.17 ^{Bb}	0.85 ± 0.21 ^{Bbc}	2.65 ± 0.43 ^{Ba}	3.49 ± 0.61 ^{Ca}
	1	0.46 ± 0.11 ^{Bc}	0.08 ± 0.01 ^{Ba}	0.54 ± 0.10 ^{Bb}	0.86 ± 0.21 ^{Bbc}	2.87 ± 0.23 ^{Ba}	3.73 ± 0.41 ^{Ba}
	4	0.80 ± 0.09 ^{Bab}	0.03 ± 0.00 ^{cd}	0.83 ± 0.09 ^{Bab}	1.62 ± 0.27 ^{ABa}	2.78 ± 0.29 ^{Ba}	4.41 ± 0.25 ^{Ca}
	7	0.89 ± 0.09 ^{ABa}	0.04 ± 0.01 ^{cd}	0.92 ± 0.09 ^{ABa}	1.30 ± 0.19 ^{Bab}	2.51 ± 0.09 ^{Ba}	3.81 ± 0.28 ^{Ca}
	10	0.98 ± 0.05 ^{ABa}	0.02 ± 0.01 ^{ABd}	1.00 ± 0.05 ^{ABa}	1.60 ± 0.03 ^{Ba}	2.70 ± 0.19 ^{Ba}	4.30 ± 0.18 ^{Ba}
UVC	0	1.06 ± 0.05 ^{Aa}	0.03 ± 0.01 ^{Bb}	1.09 ± 0.05 ^{Aab}	1.67 ± 0.05 ^{Aa}	4.17 ± 0.46 ^{Aa}	5.84 ± 0.51 ^{ABa}
	1	0.84 ± 0.02 ^{Ab}	0.07 ± 0.01 ^{Ba}	0.91 ± 0.02 ^{Ab}	1.17 ± 0.16 ^{ABb}	3.53 ± 0.49 ^{ABa}	4.70 ± 0.66 ^{ABa}
	4	1.12 ± 0.07 ^{Aa}	0.03 ± 0.01 ^b	1.15 ± 0.07 ^{Aa}	1.57 ± 0.04 ^{Bab}	3.64 ± 0.28 ^{ABa}	5.21 ± 0.30 ^{BCa}
	7	1.06 ± 0.02 ^{Aa}	0.03 ± 0.02 ^b	1.10 ± 0.01 ^{Aa}	1.60 ± 0.17 ^{ABa}	3.26 ± 0.36 ^{ABa}	4.86 ± 0.49 ^{BCa}
	10	1.07 ± 0.08 ^{Aa}	0.03 ± 0.00 ^{Ab}	1.10 ± 0.09 ^{Aa}	1.89 ± 0.10 ^{ABa}	3.48 ± 0.34 ^{ABa}	5.37 ± 0.35 ^{Aa}
UVB	0	0.96 ± 0.09 ^{Aa}	0.07 ± 0.02 ^{Ab}	1.03 ± 0.10 ^{Aab}	1.97 ± 0.05 ^{Aa}	4.56 ± 0.21 ^{Aa}	6.53 ± 0.15 ^{Aa}
	1	0.71 ± 0.03 ^{Ab}	0.11 ± 0.00 ^{Aa}	0.83 ± 0.03 ^{Ab}	1.45 ± 0.18 ^{Ab}	3.55 ± 0.44 ^{ABb}	5.00 ± 0.55 ^{ABb}
	4	0.92 ± 0.11 ^{ABa}	0.04 ± 0.01 ^{bc}	0.96 ± 0.10 ^{ABab}	2.03 ± 0.22 ^{ABa}	3.96 ± 0.41 ^{Aab}	5.99 ± 0.46 ^{ABab}
	7	0.97 ± 0.04 ^{Aa}	0.01 ± 0.01 ^{cd}	0.98 ± 0.03 ^{Aab}	1.86 ± 0.18 ^{Aab}	3.45 ± 0.44 ^{Ab}	5.30 ± 0.59 ^{ABb}
	10	1.04 ± 0.04 ^{Aa}	0.01 ± 0.00 ^{Bd}	1.05 ± 0.04 ^{Aa}	1.84 ± 0.10 ^{ABab}	3.36 ± 0.29 ^{ABb}	5.21 ± 0.22 ^{Ab}
UVC+B	0	0.30 ± 0.12 ^{Bc}	0.08 ± 0.01 ^{Aab}	0.38 ± 0.11 ^{Bc}	1.11 ± 0.25 ^{Bcd}	3.39 ± 0.71 ^{ABa}	4.50 ± 0.95 ^{BCb}
	1	0.75 ± 0.12 ^{Aab}	0.11 ± 0.01 ^{Aa}	0.86 ± 0.11 ^{Aab}	1.44 ± 0.27 ^{Abc}	3.96 ± 0.41 ^{Aa}	5.39 ± 0.65 ^{Aab}
	4	0.94 ± 0.06 ^{ABa}	0.03 ± 0.01 ^c	0.97 ± 0.05 ^{ABa}	2.12 ± 0.18 ^{Aa}	4.42 ± 0.55 ^{Aa}	6.54 ± 0.61 ^{Aa}
	7	0.76 ± 0.10 ^{Bab}	0.02 ± 0.01 ^c	0.78 ± 0.11 ^{Bab}	1.92 ± 0.11 ^{Aab}	4.06 ± 0.31 ^{Aa}	5.99 ± 0.07 ^{Aab}
	10	0.82 ± 0.06 ^{Ba}	0.02 ± 0.01 ^{ABc}	0.84 ± 0.07 ^{Bab}	2.07 ± 0.19 ^{Aab}	3.83 ± 0.51 ^{Aa}	5.89 ± 0.34 ^{Aab}

397 Different capital letters denote significant differences (p<0.05) among different treatments for the same sampling time. Different lowercase letters denote significant differences
398 (p<0.05) among different sampling times for the same treatment. Absence of letters indicates that there are no significant differences (p<0.05).

400 4. DISCUSSION

401 Regarding the microbial load, it was maintained quite constant throughout the refrigerated
402 period without differences **through storage time**. This tendency was also observed by
403 Castillejo et al. (2021) reporting higher microbial counts.

404 After the analysis of the epiphytic microflora growth throughout shelf-life, it was
405 concluded that the UV doses used were enough to prevent the **exponential** increase of the
406 microbial growth while not inducing any UV damage to the tissues. Furthermore, UVC
407 illumination is mainly used in sanitation due to the high germicidal properties of this UV
408 radiation, being considered as a sustainable alternative to conventional chemical
409 treatments. **The psychrophilic and enterobacteria load obtained after UV application**
410 **remarked that there was not a synergic effect in load when UVC and UVB were jointly**
411 **applied**. In this way, although this reduction was specific after the treatment and it was
412 not maintained throughout the shelf-life study, our results agree with those previously
413 reported in fresh-cut carrots using the same UV doses by Formica-Oliveira et al. (2017a).
414 As presumed, UVB did not show any germicidal **effect** when applied alone.

415 **As our results show, a higher dry biomass has been related to the increased content in**
416 **bioactive compounds in *Brassicaceae* sprouts, which has been also described by Šamec**
417 **et al. (2018).**

418 From a general point of view, the TPC increased after UVC and UVC+B treatments on
419 minimally processed broccoli and radish sprouts, respectively, which is a directly
420 response to the application of postharvest abiotic stresses like radiation (Cisneros-
421 Zevallos 2003). **After the application of UV-B, plants undergo an acclimatisation period**
422 **at cellular level during which an increase in phenols is produced as a defence mechanism**
423 **(Jenkins, 2017)**. Phenolics, as absorber compounds, are accumulated in the vacuoles of

424 epidermal cells in response to UV lighting and decrease the penetration of the radiation
425 into deeper cell layers (Avena-Bustillos et al., 2012). The phenol biosynthesis has been
426 linked to the phenylalanine ammonia lyase (PAL) activation after abiotic stresses caused
427 by reactive oxygen species (ROS) as signalling substances (Cisneros-Zevallos and
428 Jacobo-Velázquez, 2020). All these processes are triggered by UV-B photoreceptor due
429 to transcriptomic changes, UVR8 being the main photoreceptor for UV-B (Jenkins, 2017,
430 2014, 2009). The dissociation from UVR8 into a monomer have been possible the
431 interaction of UVR8 with CONSTITUTIVELY PHOTOMORPHOGENIC1 (COP1). In
432 this way, this interaction relays the UV-B signal to the following components of pathways
433 (Parihar et al., 2015; Singh et al., 2014).

434 Furthermore, UVC treatment also reported significant increases of TPC in broccoli
435 sprouts after treatments on day 0 and 1 and in radish sprouts on day 4. This results agree
436 with recent findings, which showed the enhancement of TPC after 7 d at 10 °C in acerola
437 fruit treated with 6 kJ m⁻² UV-C (Rabelo et al., 2020). Therefore, the abiotic stress
438 induced by the UV radiation, either single or combination of UV-C and UV-B, have
439 stimulated the biosynthesis of phenolics, which may be due to the increase of the ROS
440 production, which is able to activate the key PAL enzyme. Under UV effect, plants
441 biosynthesise antioxidant compounds as endogenous defence mechanisms, which
442 produce radical oxygen species (ROS). The effect of these substances and enzymes is
443 prolonged during storage (from 0 to 10 d) and higher levels of phenolic compound are
444 accumulated during this time to protect the plant to the end of the shelf life (Moreira-
445 Rodríguez et al., 2017a).

446 Our TAC values agree with those previously reported by other authors, who measured
447 the TPC and TAC by DPPH of broccoli and radish sprouts (De la Fuente et al. 2019;

448 Pająk et al. 2014). In this sense, the TAC measured by DPPH was highly correlated to
449 TPC with $R^2 = 0.9620$ in broccoli sprouts and $R^2 = 0.8991$ in radish sprouts.

450 As previously discussed for TPC, the UV treatments also increased the TAC in the studied
451 samples, **which may be due the fact of numerous protective reactions triggered by UV-B**
452 **that increase antioxidants to ameliorate possible DNA damaged (Jenkins, 2014; Parihar**
453 **et al., 2015)**. In fact, the TAC behaviour of samples during the refrigerated storage period
454 was similar to the TPC, since the biosynthesis of UV-absorbing compounds is the most
455 common way to fight against damaging caused by UV radiation (Nguyen et al., 2020).
456 Hence, secondary metabolites responsible of the TAC are accumulated in the surface cells
457 in response to these treatments. For this reason, minimally processed broccoli and radish
458 sprouts are considered an excellent ‘super food’, **whose** antioxidant properties could be
459 even enhanced with a postharvest UV treatment, either UV-B, UV-C, or **their**
460 combination.

461 Regarding glucosinolate content, broccoli sprouts are between 10 and 100-fold richer in
462 GLs in comparison with the adult plant (Pérez-Balibrea et al., 2011; Valente Pereira et
463 al., 2002).

464 The increase of the total GLs after UVB treatment, agree with previous **findings**, which
465 have also shown this behaviour in broccoli florets (Duarte-Sierra et al. 2020; Formica-
466 Oliveira et al. 2017b) and fresh-cut carrots (Formica-Oliveira et al. 2017a). In addition, a
467 positive effect of UV-B lighting during the preharvest period has been also reported by
468 several authors, regarding the biosynthesis of GLs in *Arabidopsis thaliana* (Neugart et
469 al., 2020) and broccoli (Moreira-Rodríguez et al., 2017a, 2017b) and kale sprouts
470 (Castillejo et al., 2021a). In fact, in response to UVB during the refrigerated storage, some
471 genes are overexpressed to activate the GL pathway, such as the tryptophan N-

472 hydroxylase (CYP79B3). This gen can be stimulated by 6-fold after low UVB doses and
473 10-fold after higher UVB doses (Duarte-Sierra et al., 2020). Besides, those high UV-B
474 doses have been also able to **increase expression of** the dihomomethionine N-hydroxylase
475 (CYP79F1) by 3-fold compared to control broccoli florets (Duarte-Sierra et al., 2020).

476 Furthermore, UVC sprouts reported similar results to UVC+B. Hence, that combination
477 did not synergistically **increase of expression of genes involve** in the GL biosynthesis.
478 Our theory to explain this behaviour is that UV-B and UV-C could share the same
479 photoreceptors in the plant. Plants have at least five types of photoreceptors, which allow
480 to perceive the light by themselves and trigger responses which prevent damage and
481 optimize the development. As previously described, UVR8 protein has been described as
482 the UV-B receptor, and its action spectrum **is ranged from 250 to 310 nm, where UV-C**
483 **region is included** (Jiang et al., 2012), which suggests that **both radiations** may share such
484 receptor. This hypothesis can also explain why low doses of UV-C can stimulate phenolic
485 compounds biosynthesis among other phytochemicals (Abdipour et al., 2019; Artés-
486 Hernández et al., 2010; Rabelo et al., 2020). This can be explained with the fact that UV-
487 C produces similar effects to UV-B or that the energy **provided** by shorter wavelengths
488 of UV-C may block the UVR8, as main UV-B receptors. **However, the spectrum action**
489 **of UVR8 may vary slightly depending on the metabolic pathway (Jiang et al., 2012). The**
490 **spectrum of action on PAL induction is closer to the UV-B region and therefore may**
491 **explain why UV-B or even UV-C+B obtained a higher increase in TPC than UV-C.**

492 As glucoraphanin level in broccoli sprouts is largely determined by genotype and the
493 environment in which the plants are grown (e.g., location, year, drought, pollution, and
494 disease pressure), and it is also higher in young plants compared to mature plants, also
495 sulforaphane content has been found in large quantities in sprouts (Pérez-Balibrea et al.,
496 2011; Valente Pereira et al., 2002; Yagishita et al., 2019). Williams et al., (2008)

497 demonstrated that ESP is responsible for producing more inactive nitrile products than
498 bioactive products during GL hydrolysis in broccoli. Furthermore, ESP activity is highest
499 in seeds and decline steadily to lower levels in mature plants. In fact, the germination of
500 broccoli seeds had no effect on the sulforaphane content.

501 The content of sulforaphene nitrile in radish sprouts of the present study was lower than
502 the biologically active compound, sulforaphene. Wang et al. (2017) observed ESP gene
503 did not shown detectable expression in any organ in radish, while NSP5 gene had not
504 expression in the roots, but a minimal expression was found in other organs. As a matter
505 of fact, the 6 % of the glucoraphenin compound was converted into sulforaphene in radish
506 sprouts. Others authors have reported the higher specific activity of myrosinase in radish
507 (Yi et al., 2016), which positively affects the ratio to ITCs from GLs in comparison with
508 broccoli. However, these low percentages corroborate the fact that some GLs are
509 metabolized into compounds that do not contribute to the evaluation of total ITCs (Hanlon
510 and Barnes, 2011). Even so, high GL content and the higher **conversion to ITCs from GLs**
511 make UVB treated radish sprouts a preferable source of sulforaphene instead of broccoli
512 sprouts. In fact, following the recommendations of 100 μ M sulforaphane daily dose for
513 healthy consumers provided by Egner et al. (2014) and Riedl, Saxon, and Diaz-Sanchez
514 (2009), an intake of 30 g of fresh UVB radish sprouts per day can be proposed to enhance
515 the detoxication of some airborne pollutants (Egner et al., 2014) and to **cause** an increase
516 in antioxidant Phase II enzymes in airway cells (Riedl et al., 2009). Similarly, a
517 consumption of 140 g of fresh UVB radish sprouts per day (500 μ M SFN daily dose) may
518 help to improve chemotherapy treatment in pancreatic cancer patients (Lozanovski et al.,
519 2014).

520 **5. CONCLUSIONS**

521 From a general point of view, a postharvest abiotic stress with UV illumination in both
522 *Brassicaceae* species showed an amelioration effect on the biosynthesis kinetics of the
523 main bioactive compounds, which some of them are well maintained throughout a shelf-
524 life period. The TPC and TAC were increased by UVB. The UVB treatment increased by
525 ~30 % the GL content compared to CTRL, which were mostly aliphatic GLs in radish
526 and indolyl GLs in broccoli. The sulforaphane content was also improved by 37.5 % in
527 UVB-treated broccoli sprouts while the sulforaphene content was highly increased by 72
528 % in UVB-treated radish sprouts. UVC and the combined application of UVC+B reported
529 similar contents of TAC, TPC and total GL content. This effect may be since UV-B and
530 UV-C share the same photoreceptors in the plant and that UV-C saturates UVR8 **avoiding**
531 the transcription of some genes that activate the biosynthesis of bioactive compounds
532 against abiotic stresses, as occurred when illuminating sprouts with low UVB doses.
533 Nevertheless, further research is needed to confirm our hypothesis. In conclusion, UVB
534 radish sprouts reported 5-fold more GLs and 60-fold more biologically active ITCs
535 content than broccoli sprouts. Therefore, we recommend the inclusion in the consumers
536 daily diet of *Brassicaceae* sprouts treated by UV radiation, which enhances the
537 concentration of potentially anti-inflammatory, anticarcinogenic, and antioxidant
538 bioactive compounds, for the prevention of chronic inflammatory diseases.

539 **DECLARATIONS**

540 **Author contributions statement**

541 Lorena Martínez-Zamora: Data curation; Formal analysis; Performed the experiments;
542 Investigation; Methodology; Writing - original draft. Noelia Castillejo: Data curation;
543 Formal analysis; Performed the experiments; Investigation; Methodology; Writing -
544 original draft. Francisco Artés-Hernández: Conceptualization; Funding acquisition;

545 Investigation; Project administration; Resources; Supervision; Validation; Visualization;
546 Writing - review & editing.

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559 **Competing interest statement**

560 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

561 **6. REFERENCES**

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770

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Author contributions statement

Lorena Martínez-Zamora: Data curation; Formal analysis; Performed the experiments; Investigation; Methodology; Writing - original draft. Noelia Castillejo: Data curation; Formal analysis; Performed the experiments; Investigation; Methodology; Writing - original draft. Francisco Artés-Hernández: Conceptualization; Funding acquisition; Investigation; Project administration; Resources; Supervision; Validation; Visualization; Writing - review & editing.

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Supplementary Material

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL PBT.docx

